

Development of Moral Values through Sports & Games

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Abstract: Sports and games have always been instrumental in the physical, moral and spiritual development of people. Their worth has been accepted throughout the world by our best teachers, social reformers and religious saints. Sports and games provide opportunities to an individual to develop his/her physical strength, endurance and capacity so that the body can be able to bear any impending problem. Swami Vivekananda asserts, "You will be nearer to Heaven through football than through the study of the Gita" (qtd. in Murty 5). Sports and Games inculcate positive traits in students who use them not only inside the field but out of it. A sportsperson learns by following paradigms of their seniors and other best players of the world across various games. He/she knows it better that sport events are as for the winning the games as they are for winning the hearts of the people and the competitors. A medal with dishonesty is looked down upon therefore; no player wants to receive it. Fair Play Trophy/ Award in each and every big international game is provided to develop good moral values in the sportspersons. Morality and sports are intertwined to each other because sports develop moral values which in turn shape the personality of an individual.

Keywords: Instrumental, physical, discipline, moral values & endurance.

We all have dreams. But in order to make dreams come into reality, it takes an awful lot of determination, dedication, self-discipline, and effort. **Jesse Owens**

Morality is a human effort to define what is right and what is wrong about our actions and thoughts. It is the sum total of those norms and principles which are universal and make human life better on our planet with an aim to exclude those which are inhuman and barbarous. These standard norms which an individual is supposed to follow to lead a good life are the best thoughts of our best persons. Morality as it relates to our behavior works on three levels. In the opinion of renowned thinker, scholar and writer C.S. Lewis, it - (1) ensures fair play and harmony between individuals; (2) helps to make us good people in order to have a good society; and (3) keeps us in a good relationship with the power that created us (qtd. in. "Morality"). Religion, sociology, philosophy, anthropology and more than these one's own conscience are some of the areas from which we receive such standard norms of morality. Hence, it is a symbol of goodness. Morality is reflected through moral values which make us civilized and cultured and guide us to lead an excellent life without harming others. These moral values can be very practically imbued in the minds of the sportspersons through their games.

Since the development of multiple modern civilizations throughout the world, sports and games play a vital role to curb the behavior of the young generations. They learn in the fields of sports what they can not learn in schools, at religious places or at their homes. Players learn moral lessons through practical ways with live examples in sports arena. They imbibe moral lessons in the fields of sports and games by way of both imitation and initiation. They learn to play the games by imitating those exemplary excellent players who were/are good in their games and display outstanding game spirit in and out of the field. They learn to play their games as it ought to be played instead of playing it in immoral ways. The first chapter a player learns in the field of sports is this that winning is not everything, but the necessary element of sports is to participate with sport spirit which is above any medal. It develops a sense of fair competition in the players. Unfair competition yields unfair result which in one way or the other makes the players feel that they are not real winners. So, this idea of fair competition teaches the players to be unbiased and fair in their private and social life in order to be a good person.

Sports and Games do not only make the players physically strong but they also sharpen their mental capacity. The popular ancient Greek proverb that a healthy mind resides in a healthy body that seems very relevant. A healthy mind always thinks about the welfare of the society. A sick and feeble body hardly develops a brilliant mind in it. Patients with deadly ailments are recovered by the power of various yogic asanas and practices. Multiple Sports activities help the sick to cope with their diseases and come back with flying colours in the mainstream of our society. Yuvraj Singh, the best player of 2011 Cricket World Cup, is the latest example who survived a cancerous tumor in his left lung. Our ancient sagas had been able to find out the best of their capabilities because of their combined physical and mental powers.

Good players always display such virtues as game spirit, discipline, cooperation, magnanimity, and respect for the rules of the games, their seniors and coaches. These virtues are integral parts of sports and games

which take shape in the psyche of a player since the time he/she starts playing. Sports instill these good qualities in players by illustrating virtues such as courage and perseverance from live examples. The endurance of a marathon runner is developed to finish the race and this same endurance is needed to be faithful in the long run of life, to remain steadfast day after day particularly on days when life seems more difficult. Sports and games are able to inculcate those virtues which are not taught by other social institutions. It is because of the reason that they lack live instances of what they preach whereas players learn it by imitating the live examples in the field. It has become the integral part of the school syllabus. Parents rely more on sports than anything else. It leaves a deep impact on their sensibility. Therefore, more and more parents are encouraging their children to join sports and games for their all-round development.

Sports and Games have capacity to change the direction of life towards positivity. As long as players are engaged in the sports activities, they refrain themselves from committing any wrong thing which would be injurious for themselves as well as for the society. They don't go to smoke and drink, they don't waste their time idly, and they don't harm anyone in any possible way. Moreover, sports and games can convert a villainous person into a full-fledged recognized personality. Amir Khan in one episode of 'Satnav Jayate' interviewed a notorious goon of Nagpur slums whose whole life is converted because of a football and now he is good football player as well as the coach of his team. He does not have time for his past bad habits because he now thinks to contribute in the development of our nation in the best possible manner

Sports and games are often used to extend cordial relations between individuals as well as countries which are arch-enemies since long time back. Players do not forget sports spirit while playing with the players of the opposite country. When four time Olympic gold medalist American athlete, Jesse Owens, was upset during the qualifying round of the broad jump event because of the sudden appearance of Carl Ludwig Long, a powerful competitor and an excellent long jumper who was hidden so far by Adolf Hitler to prove his Aryan supremacy in the Berlin Olympic in 1936, and he missed his two qualifying chances and left with the last chance to qualify, Ludwig came to him and said very politely that he could qualify easily if he jumped one foot behind the take off board. Following Long's advice, Jesse Owens not only qualified for the final round but he also won the gold medal of broad jump event. Thereafter, he states, "I won the medal but it is Luz Long who won the heart...you can melt down all the medals and cups I have and they wouldn't be plating on the 24-karat friendship I felt for Luz Long at that moment. Hitler must have gone crazy watching us embrace" (Wikipedia). Players learn to play for the team if they play in team games. They learn better the lessons of unity on the sports grounds than anywhere else. This attribute teaches them to join together not for the sake of individual benefits but for the benefit of the whole team. They reflect the same team spirit in their day today life. Leadership qualities are developed in the players due to playing in such team games. A captain of the team has to face many challenges to lead it to the victory. He learns how to keep the players of different backgrounds together so that they may not feel awkward and play with their full potential for their team. He has to surpass multiple obstacles to make the team resolute in its determination. Players in general and the team captain in particular learn to develop the quality of quick decision making. They very well know that a little mistake in the execution of their skills would bring a big misfortune to their fate. Sometimes while playing, they don't have much time to think and consult with their team members about the tactics of the game so they instantly apply the best technique to come out of such situations. Players use this art of quick decision making in their general lives whereas common people keep on thinking and remaining in the situations of "to be or not to be" for quite a long time over petty matters.

Discipline is another powerful trait which players learn from the fields of sports and games. It is unthinkable for a player to get big successes with being disciplined. A player learns to reach to the ground timely, follow the training schedule strictly, listen to the suggestions of senior players and coaches and stick to them for the optimum benefit and achieving the highest level of the game. A player is expected to work rigorously inside the field without any grudge against anyone. He should be very punctual and regular in his training. Such traits of punctuality, regularity, discipline play vital role in the development of one's personal life. Players maintain a culture of mutual respect in which they learn to respect their seniors and love and guide their juniors. Juniors learn various methods and techniques of sports by following their seniors. Thus, a kind of brotherhood is developed between those who come from diverse classes, religions, castes, ethnicities and backgrounds. They do not respect their seniors out of compulsion as is seen in many other social institutions but it is spontaneous which comes unrestrictedly from the depth of their heart. These qualities which they reflect at their homes and in the society help in cementing multiple social bonds.

Honesty is inculcated in the minds of players when they see and find that the dishonesty only results in doom and destruction of their careers. One of the best forms of honesty is to be honest to one's own self and players learn this in sports ground. They work honestly in the fields to perform well in their games. They know the importance of consistently working in the sports ground and they never ran away from here. A player who does not play honestly is looked down upon by their teammates who somehow or other want to get rid of such a player. Endurance is another quality which is developed by sports and games. A player needs great endurance capacity during performance of their games. He learns to get up after every fall because of his belief that such

hitches are not impediments but stairs in the path of success. The stories of our best sportspersons tell us that they too faced countless difficulties in their way of success but they did not deviate. This capability of sports does not only teach to the sportspersons but also common people that they should not accept defeat without putting a great struggle for victory.

Good players learn to accept victory and defeat equally because they know it well that these are the two sides of the same coin. When a player wins, he enjoys the moment but when he is defeated in a game, he learns from it his shortcomings and improves upon them so that he may not repeat them again. When he overcomes his adversity, he learns that life is not always easy and it's best to stay with difficult tasks and conquer them rather than take the easy way out. A player applies the same rules whenever he needs them in his general life. Jesse Owens state:

In the end, it's extra effort that separates a winner from second place. But winning takes a lot more than that, too. It starts with complete command of the fundamentals. Then it takes desire, determination, discipline, and self-sacrifice. And finally, it takes a great deal of love, fairness and respect for your fellow man. Put all these together, and even if you don't win, how can you lose? (Wikiquote)

Resolution is another trait which sportspersons learn from the field of sports and games. A player has to stick to his/her training schedule for quite a long time without any deviation to achieve higher successes in life. He learns how one has to sacrifice many pleasant things of one's life in order to be the top ranker in any field of life from sports arena. Sports and games do not only teach us to be fit physically but they make us solid in every sphere of life. Parents now have shifted from the popular saying that a baby is spoiled when he/she will play a game and they are willing to send their kids to join various kinds of games not only in hope of getting success in terms of winning medals at various competitive levels but because of their faith that sports activities are able to frame the character of their kids in a positive direction and more than this help them to be a good human being.

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